

Correlation of PI-RADS Scoring with Gleason's Score on 3T Multiparametric MRI in Prostatic Carcinoma with Elevated PSA Levels

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Abstract:

Introduction: Prostate cancer is the second most cancer type in men globally. Multiparametric MRI (mpMRI) PI-RADS scoring has an important role not only in the diagnosis and also estimate the lesion extent and severity of prostatic cancer.

Aim: To assess the multiparametric 3T MRI in the diagnosis of prostatic lesions in cases with elevated PSA levels and its correlation Gleason's score.

Materials and Methods: This prospective observational study consists of a total of 36 cases with chief complaints of obstructive lower urinary tract symptoms above 50 years of age; with raised prostate specific antigen (PSA) levels were recruited. Radiological examinations included 2D T2 weighted images (T2W-MRI), dynamic contrast enhancement score (DCE-MRI), and diffusion weighted images (DWI) were assessed.

Results: The mean ADC values of tumors with Gleason's score >7 was $0.67 \pm 0.12 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, tumors with Gleason's score 7 was $0.78 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, and tumors with Gleason's score <6 was $0.84 \pm 0.28 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. The mpMRI PIRADS score 3 was noticed in 8.33% cases, PIRADS score 4 was seen in 41.67% cases and PIRADS score 5 was seen in 50% cases. The overall outcome values of Gleason's score and mpMRI PI-RADS score showed a sensitivity of 70.12%, specificity of 84.65%, positive predictive value of 79.36%, negative predictive value of 87.94% and kappa value of 0.57.

Conclusion: There is a positive correlation between Gleason's score and PIRADS score and a significant negative correlation between Gleason's score and mean ADC value of prostatic tumor. This approach is effective in distinguishing the extent and severity of the condition. The implication of mpMRI PIRADS scoring in the context of elevated PSA levels can reduce the unwanted biopsy and economic burden to the patients.

Keywords: Prostatic carcinoma, Multiparametric MRI, PIRADS scoring, Gleason's score, PSA levels.

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Introduction

Prostatic carcinoma is the most leading cancer type diagnosed in men [1]. Traditionally, the diagnosis of prostatic cancers is conducted by transrectal USG guided biopsy which depend on transrectal USG, digital rectal examination and PSA levels.

This procedure may lead to misdiagnosis of the tumor extent, severity which causes failure inaccurate treatment provision. Diagnosis of prostatic lesions with TRUS guided biopsy and digital rectal examination has poor sensitivity and specificity and positive predictive value [2].

In current trends, 3-T multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging (mpMRI) is a widely used non-invasive method in the diagnosis, staging and grading of prostatic cancer [3]. It is a non-invasive MRI technique that uses T2 weighted images (T2W-MRI), dynamic contrast enhancement score (DCE-MRI), diffusion weighted images (DWI) which

improve the diagnostic accuracy [4]. European society of urogenital radiology (ESUR) has framed a structured reporting system i.e. prostate imaging reporting and data system (PI-RADS) for the assessment of dubious prostatic lesions on MRI [5]. Gleason's scoring system is a high grade histopathological method in the assessment of the extent and severity of prostatic lesions. Gleason's score <6 indicate low grade tumor, 7 indicate intermediate grade tumor and >7 indicate high grade tumors [6].

There is a literature lack in the correlation of multiparametric 3T MRI PIRADS score with Gleason's score. The present study was designed to assess the multiparametric 3T MRI in the diagnosis of prostatic lesions in cases with elevated PSA levels and its correlation Gleason's score.

Material and Methods

The present prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Pratima Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar from January 2023 to February 2024. A total of 36 cases with a chief complaint of obstructive lower urinary tract symptoms attending the department of General medicine were recruited.

Cases above 50 years of age, with raised prostate specific antigen levels and willingness to participate in the study were included. Cases with bleeding disorders, urinary tract infections, claustrophobia, with implants and not willing to participate were excluded. The study participants were explained the indication and risk of the procedure. A sufficient time was given to each participant to clarify their doubts about the study procedure. After the detailed explanation, informed consent was obtained from all the study participants and the study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee. All the cases were undergone with multiparametric MRI on a 3-tesla whole body scanner (SEIMENS, Germany) with phased array

body coil. Radiological examinations included lesion location, the volume of the prostate, 2D T2 weighted images (T2W-MRI), dynamic contrast enhancement score (DCE-MRI), diffusion weighted images (DWI) and MRSI was assessed.

MRI Image sets were analysed by three experienced radiologists and extracted the final PI-RADS score. We adopted the PI-RADS scoring system for Multiparametric MRI components.

The scoring system was framed according to the guidelines of the European society for urogenital radiology (EUSR). The PI-RADS scoring system is a 5 point Likert scale system. The scoring system has a total composite score out of 20 involving all components i.e. T2WI, DCE, DWI and MRSI.

All the study participants were advised for a TRUS scan to collect biopsies of the prostate gland. Gleason’s score was collected by histopathological examination of the TRUS guided biopsy specimens. The prostate gland tumours were classified into three groups according to Gleason’s score.

Table 1: Division of prostate tumours according to Gleason’s score

Gleason’s score	Grade of tumors
<6	Low grade tumors
7	Intermediate grade tumors
>7	High grade tumors

The SPSS version 23.0 software was used to carry out statistical analysis relevant to the study. Descriptive statistics were used to represent demographic and clinical characteristics in the form of frequency and percentages. Spearman’s

correlation was applied to assess the relationship between two variables.

P<0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

Figure 1: Age wise distribution of Cases with prostatic lesions

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of study parameters

Parameter	Mean ± SD
Prostate volume (cc)	47.22 ± 13.60
ADC	0.76 ± 0.34
PSA (ng/ml)	39.18 ± 29.36

Table 3: Radiological and histopathological outcome data of study participants

Parameter	Frequency	Percentage
mpMRI PI-RADS Score		
Intermediate chance (score 3)	03	8.33%
Medium chances malignant score (4)	15	41.67%
High chances of malignancy (score 5)	18	50%
Gleason's score		
Score 6	08	22.2%
Score 7	10	27.8%
Score 8	08	22.2%
Score 9	11	30.5%
Outcome of HPE		
High (Gleason's score >7)	18	50%
Intermediate (Gleason's score 7)	10	27.8%
Low (Gleason's score <6)	08	22.2%

Table 4: comparison of mean ADC values with Gleason's score

Gleason's score	Mean ± SD (ADC)	p- value
score >7	0.67 ± 0.12	0.002
score 7	0.78 ± 0.10	
score <6	0.84 ± 0.28	

Table 5: Correlation of outcome values between Gleason's score and PI-RADS score.

Outcome	Gleason's score/PI-RADS score		
	Score <6/3	Score 7/4	Score >7/5
Sensitivity	54%	79.2%	84.65%
Specificity	99.8%	75.9	89.27%
Positive predictive value	99.9%	58.21	85.46%
Negative predictive value	89.5%	86.42	88.36%
Kappa value	0.58	0.55	0.62
p-value	0.0281	0.0244	0.0458

Figure 2: Overall outcome of present study

Discussion

Among the study participants, 18 cases were between 61-70 years, 12 cases were between 50-60 years and 6 cases were above 70 years. The mean age was 67.58 years (Figure 1). The mean and SD of prostate volume was 47.22 ± 13.60 , serum Prostate specific antigen (PSA) level was 39.18 ± 29.36 and apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) was 0.76 ± 0.34 (Table 2). A study by Valentina Brancato et al. noticed a mean PSA level in PIRADS 3 was 10.36ng/ml and in PIRADS 4 was 8.56ng/ml. The prostatic volume in PIRADS 3 was 55.76 cm^3 and in PIRADS 4 was 55.6 cm^3 [7].

In the present study, all the participants were directed to TRUS biopsy. Among the cases 22.2% cases reported Gleason's score 6, 27.8% reported Gleason's score 7, 22.2% cases reported Gleason's score 8 and 30.5% cases reported Gleason's score 9. The mpMRI PIRADS score 3 was noticed in 8.33% cases, PIRADS score 4 was seen in 41.67% cases and PIRADS score 5 was seen in 50% cases (Table 3).

In this study, the mean ADC values of tumors with Gleason's score >7 was $0.67 \pm 0.12 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, tumors with Gleason's score 7 was $0.78 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, and tumors with Gleason's score <6 was $0.84 \pm 0.28 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$. The mean difference of ADC value of tumors was statistically significant with Gleason's score 7 and >7 (Table 4). A study by Thomas Hambroek et al. noticed that the median ADC values had a negative relationship with Gleason's grade group. The mean difference between Gleason's grade groups was statistically significant [8]. A study by Maheen Anwar SS et al. noticed a mean ADC value for tumors with Gleason's score 6 was $935 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ (SD = $248.4 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$); Gleason score of 7 was $837 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ (SD = $208.5 \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$) [10].

A study by Yoshimitsu K et al. noticed mean ADC value of tumor with Gleason's score of <6 was $1.19 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, Gleason's score of 7 was $1.10 \pm 0.24 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and Gleason's score >7 was $0.93 \pm 0.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ [11]. A study by Yagci AB et al. study showed that there was a significant decrease in ADC value with an increase in tumor grade and mean ADC for tumors with Gleason's score of <6 was $1.18 \pm 0.44 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, Gleason's score of 7 was $1.05 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ and Gleason's score >7 was $0.84 \pm 0.16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ [14]. The overall outcome values of Gleason's score and mpMRI PI-RADS score showed a sensitivity of 70.12%, specificity of 84.65%, the positive predictive value of 79.36%, the negative predictive value of 87.94% and kappa value of 0.57.

A study by Valentina Brancato et al. concluded that mpMRI 2T and ADC radiomic features are effective for the detection of prostatic lesion scores

as PIRADS 3 and 4 [7]. A study by Thomas Hambroek et al. concluded that ADC at 3T MRI showed an inverse relationship to Gleason's grades in peripheral zone prostate cancer [8]. A study by Fuat Kizilay et al. concluded that the higher PIRADS score may be an important predictor for poor prognostic factors which indicates prostatic cancers, in addition to disease recurrence and requirement of additional care [9].

A study by Maheen Anwar SS et al. concluded that ADC values are effective in the differentiation of tumors with Gleason's score 6 (Minimal risk), 7 (Moderate risk), 8 and 9 (High risk) [10]. A study by Wibulpolprasert P et al. concluded that multiparametric MRI with PIRADS 2 has the highest sensitivity concerning detection of larger lesions with Gleason's score >7 or 7 [11]. A study by Bektic J et al. concluded that PIRADS score level of >10 is a key threshold for a positive tumor diagnosis [12]. A study by Yoshimitsu K et al. concluded that T2WI/ADC map reading was effective than T2WI reading in prostatic cancer detection and localization [13]. In this study, there is a positive correlation between Gleason's score and PIRADS score and a significant negative correlation between Gleason's score and mean ADC value of prostatic tumor. A study by Heath Liddell et al. concluded that prostate examination by mpMRI 3T as PIRADS 3 are associated with a low incidence of the presence of clinically significant prostate cancer [15].

Conclusion

The results of present study concluded that mpMRI PIRADS scoring is crucial, attainable and noninvasive approach and has high sensitivity, specificity in the diagnosis of prostatic carcinoma in cases with elevated PSA levels. This approach is effective in distinguishing the extent and severity of the condition. Implication of mpMRI PIRADS scoring in context of elevated PSA levels can reduce the unwanted biopsy and economic burden to the patients.

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